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Abstract

The activities of WP6 are devoted to servification, virtualization and remotization of existing tools and services available from the four involved Research Infrastructures (CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS) in H2IOSC. The document first describes objectives and state of the art, then lists refactoring processes carried out, involving servification steps, specifications and protocols adopted to improve access of WP6 services.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

RI	Research Infrastructure (CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS or OPERAS, in this document)
H2IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud
CC	Cloud Computing
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
CLARIN-IT	CLARIN Italian node (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure)
DARIAH-IT	DARIAH Italian node (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities)
E-RIHS	E-RIHS Italian node (European Heritage Science Research Infrastructure)
OPERAS	OPERAS Italian node (Open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
REST	Representational State Transfer
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
VM	Virtual Machine
OAS	OpenAPI specification
OAD	OpenAPI description (or document)

SSO

Single sign-on

Introduction

The H2IOSC project aims at creating a federated and inclusive cluster of research infrastructures in the ESFRI domain of Social Sciences and Humanities (formerly Social and Cultural Innovation). Specifically, the four involved Research Infrastructures (RIs) are: CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS. The Work Package 6 is devoted to activities related to servification, virtualization and remotization of existing tools and services available from the four involved RIs in H2IOSC.

Objectives

The main goal of activities carried out in the WP6 is to **improve (or enable) access** to rich **tools and services** provided by involved RIs. As already highlighted in D6.1, some of the tools are not yet properly accessible to different communities of researchers, or they are not yet servified.

D6.2 outlines a plan to improve access to the instruments and services offered by the RIs involved in the H2IOSC project. This plan involves: i) the servification of tools, which means making them accessible as services in the H2IOSC cloud, ii) the virtualization of those that cannot be servified, iii) the remotization, enabling remote control of scientific instruments. The main objective of the activities carried out in WP6 is to improve (or enable) access to the rich tools and services provided by the RIs involved. Following the operational plan for *servification, virtualization, and remotization* introduced in D6.1 and summarized in the following paragraphs, D6.2 describes detailed strategies adopted by the involved RIs and units to strengthen access to services through specific refactoring actions.

Challenges

The variety of tools and services offered by CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS, and OPERAS, described in D6.1, highlight several challenges: The first challenge faced was related to the different domains, target users and scientific objectives of the existing tools offered by the participating RIs. A second challenge is related to the different level of maturity and readiness as evidenced in the current RI offerings. This translates into different efforts and pace on the part of specific RIs/OU's to align a given service with the common WP6 requirements, or to servify a given tool. Another challenge is represented by applications hosted on-premise, as opposed to hosted by a public cloud platform or remote data center. This is quite common for some specialized software tools deployed within labs (or entire RIs). This class often presents significant challenges in terms of servification (e.g.: additional or intensive effort) also due to maintenance, (lack of) access to source code, or poor extensibility.

Servification and Virtualization

Based on the results gathered by WP2, WP6 first aim was to classify and parameterize the current internal offering of tools and services available to each RI. This task was inspired by ongoing work related to the IPERION-HS project in E-RIHS to explore methods to improve interoperability among Heritage Science data. Another reference is the current classification in the EOSC portal, that will provide unified access to a European hub of research data, tools, and services for innovation and education-especially software and services. This initial

classification is also particularly useful for mapping the current state of the art concerning servification and providing a first reference to measure the effort required for the refactoring activities. Due to the diversity of tools and services, this effort will be uneven and should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis. Basic information by tool/service included: title, description, category, vendor, RI, keywords, reference links (repositories, active instances, etc.), standards employed, input/output (if applicable). Mapping input/output classes (also one of the key performance indicators in WP6) was particularly important for service composition. For example, such classification should facilitate future automated agents to provide combined solutions for user-given scenarios or to provide recommendations from specific queries or resource types.

Regarding the specific cases of on-premise software tools used among the participating RIs, refactoring may not be a viable solution because of: 1) major efforts required, 2) lack of access to the code, or 3) major reengineering issues. In these cases, virtualization was the preferred choice, working in close coordination with WP4 to make these tools accessible to the reference scientific communities.

Category mapping for each WP6 service was particularly important in determining the scientific areas covered by all RIs when fully implemented and offered to the community at the federation level. Refactoring activities targeting servification are intended to improve (or enable) access to various scientific communities: as highlighted in the internal classification, different levels of maturity, adopted technologies, and target communities emerged.

To enable (or improve) discovery of services capabilities, as anticipated in D6.1, a *service manifest* was designed to provide a “surface descriptor”, specifically targeting integrations at federation level (like Marketplace in WP5) or local to RI. Regarding the internal refactoring plan, the first step was to identify the minimum set of functions required by each service with respect to the target community, including routines, procedures or features that users need to access. A second step involved investigating access policies by service, including existing authentication protocols, where applicable, to access specific resources.

A further step was also planned towards the consolidation of the H2IOSC federation, through SSO (single-sign on) being investigated in WP4 and also discussed in WP5 (Marketplace). The following steps involve the translation of these selected routines into *accessible endpoints* per service, following existing REST API guidelines and best practices: independence, evolution, and API design organized around resources. The REST refactoring APIs for each service and the strategies adopted will be described in detail in this document.

Remotization

Remotization protocols are being developed to perform remote scientific and technical investigations of artworks using hyperspectral analytical techniques available in E-RIHS' MOLAB platform. The remote control of experimental operations was designed through a series of closely interconnected components: cyber-physical systems/devices (machines and sensors), middleware (communications and data transfer), cloud (remote data processing and remote VE) and software. The prototype design of the remotization platform consists of: cyberphysical devices (in situ), middleware, remote control, software.

State of the Art

REST (representational state transfer) is the architecture used for designing services consumed across different platforms and environments fuelling interoperability (Ehsan et al. 2022, Li et al. 2016).

The two main properties of this architecture are *statelessness* and *cross-platform consumption readiness*: it is nowadays a widely followed and standardized way of publishing services over the Internet. REST emerged as the standard protocol for implementing and consuming these services, which are called RESTful application programming interfaces (APIs). Various surveys did show that various companies have migrated in recent years from XML-supported SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol) to REST (Kumar et al. 2023), thus making such adoption quite straightforward for newly crafted services.

HTTP verbs in particular plays a fundamental role in determining how clients interact with resources. These standardized HTTP methods, often referred to as HTTP verbs, are at the core of RESTful services, as building blocks of REST API interactions:

GET	used to request data from the server. It is a safe and idempotent operation, meaning it should not have any side effects on the server, and multiple identical GET requests should produce the same result
POST	used to create a new resource on the server. When a client sends a POST request, it typically includes data in the request body that the server uses to create a new resource
PUT	used to update an existing resource on the server. It requires the client to send the entire representation of the resource, even if only a small part of it is being modified
PATCH	used to update an existing resource on the server (like PUT), but it requires the client to send partial data to modify part of the resource
DELETE	is used to remove a resource from the server. When a client sends a DELETE request, it instructs the server to eliminate the specified resource

These verbs can be mapped to specific actions to be performed on resources: *retrieval* (GET); *creation* (POST); *update* (PUT/PATCH); *deletion* (DELETE). There are also two important concepts related to HTTP verbs: *idempotency* and *safety*.

1. *Idempotency*: an operation is idempotent if performing it multiple times has the same effect as performing it once. GET is inherently idempotent, while PUT and DELETE can be idempotent if designed properly. POST, on the other hand, is not idempotent, as creating a new resource each time will have a different effect
2. *Safety*: a safe operation is one that does not modify the state of the server. GET is considered a safe operation, as it does not change anything on the server. However, POST, PUT, and DELETE are not safe, as they can alter server state

The **OpenAPI**¹ Specification (OAS) defines a standard, language-agnostic interface to HTTP APIs which allows humans and computers to discover the capabilities of a service without access to source code, documentation, or through network traffic inspection. When properly defined, a consumer can understand and interact with the remote service with a minimal amount of implementation logic. An OpenAPI definition (also referred as OpenAPI document or description – or OAD for short) can be used by documentation generation tools to display the API, code generation tools to generate servers and clients in various programming languages, testing tools, and many other use cases.

¹ <https://www.openapis.org/>

Figure 1: sample Pet Store Server based on the OpenAPI 3.0 specification

OAS does not require rewriting existing APIs, nor binding any software to a service – the described service may not even be owned by the creator of its description. However, the service's capabilities need to be described in the structure of the OAS. The OpenAPI Specification does not mandate a specific development process such as design-first or code-first. It does facilitate either technique by establishing clear interactions with an HTTP API.

OpenAPI Specification also provides:

- A non-proprietary format
- The most developed tooling ecosystem: as a direct result of the previous statement, OpenAPI offers a vast number of tools to work with it
- A format readable by both machines and humans, in the form of OpenAPI descriptors (OADs)

Containerization is a lightweight virtualization technology allowing the deployment and execution of distributed applications on cloud, edge/fog, and Internet-of-Things platforms (Casalicchio & Iannucci, 2020). Each container is a fully functional and portable computing environment surrounding the application and keeping it isolated from other environments (for instance running in parallel on the same server/machine). There are many widely proven advantages offered by containerization:

- easier management of the life cycle of distributed applications
- negligible overhead for when they run either on bare-metal or virtual servers
- (re)start / stop times reduced up to an order of magnitude with respect to virtual machines (VMs)

Docker² is an open platform for developing, shipping, and running applications. It allows to separate *applications* from *infrastructure*, accelerating the delivery process. Docker streamlines the development lifecycle by allowing developers to work in standardized environments using local containers which provide your applications and services (Potdar et al. 2020).

Docker's container-based platform allows for highly portable workloads: a *docker container* is an isolated environment where an application runs without affecting the rest of the system and without the system impacting the application. Since they are isolated, containers are well-suited for securely running software like databases or web applications requiring access to sensitive resources, without giving access to every user on the system. They can run on a developer's local laptop, on physical or virtual machines in data-centers, on cloud providers, or in a mixture of environments.

Docker images are read-only templates containing instructions for creating a container: it creates containers to run on the Docker platform. An image is composed of multiple stacked layers, like layers in a photo editor, each changing something in the environment. Images contain the code or binary, runtimes, dependencies, and other filesystem objects to run an application

² <https://www.docker.com/>

Service Manifests

Given the challenges already highlighted - including the variety of domains involved, target communities and technologies - the definition of WP6 service manifests (carried out by task 6.1) was further refined, together with all the RIs involved.

As anticipated in D6.1, the manifest serves as a “*surface descriptor*” enabling discovery of the properties and capabilities of a given service, intended for specific integrations such as Marketplace developed in WP5 or local RI catalogues. The manifest structural model is aligned across the four RIs, within the H2IOSC federation, to provide consistent and robust access to service properties and capabilities.

The manifest model was developed based on several activities, including:

1. Preliminary activities of WP6 (described in D6.1) and their intersection with the activities of other WPs (such as WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5)
2. Existing national/international schemas
3. Ongoing efforts in current or past projects (already introduced in D6.1)

More specifically, the general schema mainly inherits attributes from the EOSC service model, the E-RIHS service model (v0.7), and the CLARIN switchboard tool schema (v2). A collaborative document was established among the RIs to refine and evolve the initial draft, including main sections, mandatory and optional attributes, type by attribute, and controlled vocabularies where required (with input from WP4 and WP3).

A corresponding translation into a JSON schema³ offers a few automation advantages in H2IOSC federation: it allows validation of new manifests (i.e., new services wishing to join the H2IOSC federation) and enables automatic generation of input forms for manifest attributes, etc. - for dedicated tools or utilities to generate service manifests. An experimental micro-service was prototyped and deployed to service providers: this was particularly useful to iterate and evolve the manifest schema among all involved RIs very quickly.

The service manifest also includes a refined input/output section of a given service (after multiple iterations with service providers), as well as dedicated technology sections developed in co-design with WP5 (Marketplace) and WP3, specifically integrating readiness levels (see section 6 of deliverable D3.2).

Among the main purposes of the manifest there's the need to provide Marketplace (as well as other H2IOSC actors) with a standardized way to:

1. Discover the capabilities of a given service
2. Present descriptive composition (e.g., suggestions on whether and how well two services A and B could be composed and their compatibility level/score)
3. Provide recommendations (e.g., depending on search queries on specific types of resources) for services composability

³ <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/phoenixbf/h2m/refs/heads/main/core/schema.json>

The manifest attributes also provide details about a given service in terms of its implementation, for comprehensive and enhanced indexing within web portals (local to RIs, but also in the joint H2IOSC Market Place).

To improve access to WP6 services, a refactoring under the surface (beyond the manifest) was also required. The next section describes such process, with specific focus on REST APIs equipment or enhancement for a given service.

Refactoring overview

This section describes WP6 internal refactoring processes carried out on each H2IOSC exposed service, based on the D6.1 guidelines, as well as the per-service OAS descriptor, accessible via service manifest as described in D6.1.

OpenAPI descriptors enable discovery of services capabilities from humans, automated harvesters, platforms or other project layers, including H2IOSC MarketPlace (developed in WP5) and its API Manager (developed in WP4).

The following macro-tasks have been identified in WP6 refactoring processes:

1. Identify a set of *functions/routines to be exposed* by the service, starting from the original status
2. Define *authentication* policies (if applicable) for the set and if/how they can be integrated with SSO designed in H2IOSC
3. Translate the set into *REST endpoints*, with proper verbs (see “state of the art” section)
4. Generate accessible OAD (*OpenAPI descriptors* - to be linked with service manifest)

To support these activities, 8 different training courses were also arranged by CNR ISPC Rome and Naples OUs, for temporary personnel recruited among the four RIs mainly operating on WP6. More specifically the courses: “Virtualization and Microservices”, “Docker Base”, “REST API”, “Data Visualization”, “Database MySQL”, “Javascript”, “Neural Networks” and “Data Science introduction”.

Regarding REST API refactoring (or equipment) the following guidelines and best practices were adopted:

- *Independence*: any client (internal or external to the H2IOSC federation) should be able to call these functionalities, regardless of how the API is implemented internally
- *Evolution*: The API should be able to evolve and add functionality independently from client applications. Existing client applications should continue to function without modification as the API evolves
- *API design* organized around resources

For asynchronous operations (e.g. service routines that might require a prolonged but finite time to complete), task managers approaches were considered to track computationally intensive operations, while providing proper interfaces or task tracking systems to keep users informed about the progress.

Regarding the OAD creation step per service, two main approaches exist when creating the OpenAPI descriptor:

1. **Code-first:** the API is first implemented in code, and then its description is created from it, using code comments, code annotations or simply written from scratch. This approach does not require developers to learn another language, so it is usually regarded as the easiest one
2. **Design-first:** the API description is written first and then the code follows. The first obvious advantages are that the code already has a skeleton upon which to build, and that some tools can provide boilerplate code automatically.

Several advantages of OpenAPI have been identified allowing automated tools to process API formally described in a machine-readable format:

- **Description Validation and Linting:** OAD can be checked for its correctness, also following specific formatting guidelines by the service provider
- **Data Validation:** the data flowing through the service API (in both directions) is correct, during development and once deployed
- **Documentation Generation:** traditional human-readable documentation can be automatically produced, based on the machine-readable description, which always stays up-to-date
- **Code Generation:** create both server and client code in any programming language, freeing developers from having to perform data validation or write SDK glue code, for example
- **Mock Servers:** Create simulated server settings providing example responses to start testing with, before refactoring activities
- **Security Analysis:** Discover possible vulnerabilities at the API design stage

All OADs (YAML or JSON) related to WP6 services must be accessible publicly (not necessarily on the same server where the service is deployed): each service provider has full control over OAD publication and its access. A dedicated WP6 table collects all OADs produced by service providers, also referenced in the corresponding WP6 service manifest.

Refactored services by participating RIs

The following table lists all the refactored services by each participating RIs. Each service details the refactoring steps performed, including architectural design (or redesign), access improvements, containerization strategies, as well as challenges encountered during such activities. A unique identifier within the H2IOSC federation will be also assigned to each service.

Service name	RI	OU	Platform
TLIO	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
Pluto	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
GATTO	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
TIGRO	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
Mirabile	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
EVT	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
RAISE	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
TRAME	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
Digital Fabrication Laboratory Virtual Access	E-RIHS	ISTI-PI	yes
Kapto (Capture services)	E-RIHS	ISPC-RM	
ATON (WebXR Services for HS)	E-RIHS	ISPC-NA/RM	yes
SENNSE	E-RIHS	ISPC LE	
AI Services	E-RIHS	ISPC CT	
Gravifix service	E-RIHS	IMATI GE	
3D Annotation service	E-RIHS	IMATI GE	
SimilarityLib	E-RIHS	IMATI GE	

LexO ItAnt	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
CASH ItAnt	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
Triple Store	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
EpiLexO ItAnt	CLARIN	ILC-PI	yes
Stanza NLP Chain	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
Stanza NLP Chain for ParlaMint	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
UDPipe	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
Named Entity Recognition (based on NameTag)	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
Federated Content Search	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
TEI Publisher + eXist-db	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
Text Aligner	CLARIN	ILC-PI	
EpiLexO Editor	CLARIN	ILC-PI	yes
eScriptorium	CLARIN	ILC-PI	yes

CLARIN

The CLARIN-IT services listed here will be displayed via the marketplace and will be documented using methods and protocols such as OpenAPI. The federation authentication service based on an AAI developed by Nanotec will be integrated, while the authorization part and related user role management will be developed at the infrastructure level.

ILC PI - LexO ItAnt - REST (micro)services for editing lexical data encoded in RDF/Turtle

LexO ItAnt: LexO ItAnt is a service for querying dictionaries in RDF format, interacts with a graphdb and is integrated within the EpiLexO interface of the ItAnt project. It is callable via HTTP calls through the use of REST APIs.

This service is categorized as Query and data extraction; Lexicon lookup and searching.

LexO is software made in Java and is an evolution of an earlier product (called LexO-lite) that provided a monolithic application (UI + Backend). Now, LexO is presented as a Web service (powered by Spring Boot) that allows it to be queried through an endpoint. The software interfaces with a mysql db (for storing some information such as users and transactions) and a triple store (such as graphDB) for handling RDF-like semantic information.

Current status

- *Completed⁴*

Refactoring activity

- This isn't a refactored service/software

Authentication

- Authentication is not implemented, but some services require a bearer token.

Endpoints

- https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/LexO-backend-itant_itant/ (CLARIN-IT endpoint)

OAD

- https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/LexO-backend-itant_itant/service/swagger.json

ILC PI - CASH ItAnt - REST (micro)services for managing and annotating TEI-EpiDoc document

CASH ItAnt: CASH ItAnt is a suite of RESTful (micro)services designed for the management and annotation of TEI-EpiDoc documents. This system enables efficient processing of structured textual data, supporting advanced workflows for digital philology and linguistic annotation within the CLARIN-IT infrastructure. It provides tools for manipulating,

⁴ Currently, the software used in the context of the ItAnt project does not correspond with the latest version of the software because the latter has been expanded in the context of another research project not inherent in this current one.

annotating, and validating TEI-EpiDoc encoded texts, ensuring interoperability and facilitating scholarly research in the digital humanities.

This service is categorized as Query and data extraction; Corpus management, exploration and processing.

CASH is a software program designed in Java (using the Spring Boot framework) and enables the storage of enrollment information encoded in TEI EpiDoc using a MySQL database.

Current status

- *Completed*

Refactoring activity

- This is not a refactored service/software

Authentication

- Authentication is not implemented, but some services require a bearer token.

Endpoints

- https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/cash_itant/swagger-ui/index.html
[configUrl=/cash_itant/v3/api-docs/swagger-config](https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/cash_itant/v3/api-docs/swagger-config) (CLARIN-IT endpoint)

OAD

- https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/cash_itant/v3/api-docs

ILC PI - SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service - A tool for publishing and exploring controlled vocabularies encoded in SKOS

SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service: SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service is a web-based tool designed for publishing and exploring controlled vocabularies encoded in SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System). It provides an intuitive interface for browsing, searching, and visualizing hierarchical or associative relationships between concepts, supporting knowledge organization and semantic interoperability in digital humanities and other domains.

This service is categorized as Data representation and visualization; Knowledge representation and visualization.

Skosmos is a software made by the National Library of Finland and is an application that is built mainly in PHP, with some elements in Javascript for dynamic management of some graphical and structural logic elements of the interface. The software communicates with a triple store through the declaration of an endpoint in the appropriate configuration file. Inside the part managed in PHP, Skosmos takes care of communicating with the graph database and organizes, according to predefined criteria, the information that will then be displayed in the interface.

Current status

- *Completed*

Refactoring activity

- This is not a refactored service/software.

Authentication

- This service does not require authentication

Endpoints

- <https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/skosmos/it/> (CLARIN-IT endpoint)

OAD

- <https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/skosmos/doc/>

ILC PI - Triple Store - A graph database for storing semantic dataset (LLOD)

Triple Store: Triple Store is a graph database solution, powered by GraphDB, designed for storing and managing semantic datasets, particularly those adhering to the Linguistic Linked Open Data (LLOD) principles. It enables efficient querying, integration, and visualization of interconnected semantic data, supporting advanced research in linguistics and digital humanities through robust RDF and SPARQL functionalities.

This service is categorized as Data representation and visualisation; Knowledge representation and visualization.

GraphDB is a highly optimized RDF triplestore developed in Java, designed to manage and query large volumes of semantic data. It supports W3C standards such as RDF, SPARQL, OWL, and SHACL, making it suitable for linked data and knowledge graph applications.

Refactoring activity

- N/A

Authentication

- This service supports local authentication.

Endpoints

- <https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/graphdb10/> (CLARIN-IT endpoint)

OAD

- <https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/graphdb10/webapi>

ILC PI - EpiLexO ItAnt - interfaces for editing, querying, visualising linked language resources for ancient languages

EpiLexO ItAnt: EpiLexO ItAnt provides interfaces for editing, querying, and visualizing linked language resources specifically tailored for ancient languages. This platform supports the

management of linguistic data, enabling researchers to create, explore, and analyze interlinked lexical and textual resources, fostering digital philology and the study of ancient languages within a linked data framework.

This service is categorized as Data representation and visualization.

The EpiLexO Editor is the editing GUI interface of the DigitAnt platform; built in Angular 11, it operates upon a set of independent software back-end components through HTTP REST API protocol, mainly the LexO-server and the CASH-server. The application is designed to facilitate collaboration among scholars, enabling multiple researchers to work simultaneously on the same datasets in cooperation. The EpiLexO GUI is organised in 3 main sections (or columns), each of them providing a set of different functionalities for different data and information types. The column on the left contains the navigation trees for the main resources: corpus, lexicon, and (lexical) concepts; the column on the right side of the interface displays several panels that contain contextual and additional information such as links to related resources, bibliography, attestations, and metadata. The central column is the main working area devoted to lexicon editing and linking operations, in its 2 horizontal panels, one for Inscriptions, the other for lexical entries.

The interface can be considered a functional working prototype, with core functionalities for lexicon processing, creation, and lookup implemented; it is currently in active use by the ItAnt project members. The interface supports basic editing and creation of linked language resources for ancient languages.

Current status

- *Completed*

Refactoring activity

- This is not a refactored service/software

Authentication

- This service requires only local authentication

Endpoints

- https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/epilexo_itant/ (CLARIN-IT endpoint)

OAD

- No OAD

ILC PI - Stanza NLP Chain (Lemmatization, Dependency Parsing, NER for the Italian Language)

Stanza NLP Chain: Stanza NLP Chain is a natural language processing pipeline designed for the Italian language, offering lemmatization, dependency parsing, and named entity recognition (NER). Built on the Stanza framework, this tool provides state-of-the-art linguistic analysis capabilities, supporting advanced research and applications in computational linguistics and language technology.

This service is categorized as Linguistic Analysis; Data processing.

This text-processing pipeline is made in Python and, based on its structure, allows only all processes to be done without being able to go only through intermediate or single steps.

Current status

- Not developed

Refactoring activity

- Early stage

Authentication

- This service does not support nor require authentication

Endpoints

- No endpoints

OAD

- N/A

ILC PI - Stanza NLP Chain for ParlaMint Data

Stanza NLP Chain for ParlaMint Data: Stanza NLP Chain for ParlaMint Data is a tailored natural language processing pipeline designed to process and analyze parliamentary corpora encoded in the ParlaMint framework. Utilizing Stanza's robust capabilities, it supports tasks such as lemmatization, dependency parsing, and named entity recognition (NER), enabling detailed linguistic and semantic analysis of structured political discourse data.

This service is categorized as Linguistic Analysis; Data processing.

This text-processing pipeline is made in Python and, based on its structure, allows only all processes to be done without being able to go only through intermediate or single steps. For servification, the Fast API library for creating Web services was used.

Current status

- *Completed*

Refactoring activity

- Conversion of the source code to python software

Authentication

- This service does not support nor require authentication

Endpoints

- <https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/parlamint-api> (CLARIN-IT endpoint)

OAD:

- <https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/parlamint-api/openapi.json>

ILC PI – UDPipe

UDPipe: UDPipe is a tool and a trainable pipeline designed for tokenization, tagging, lemmatization, and dependency parsing of text. It is built on Universal Dependencies (UD), making it suitable for processing texts in multiple languages. UDPipe is efficient, customizable, and widely used in natural language processing (NLP) tasks, enabling researchers and developers to analyse and preprocess linguistic data with high accuracy. UDPipe is language-agnostic and can be trained given annotated data in CoNLL-U format. Trained models are provided for nearly all UD treebanks.

This service is categorized as Linguistic Analysis; tokenization; tagging; lemmatization; dependency parsing.

Current status

Refactoring activity is under evaluation as it will be deployed by using LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ guidelines.

Refactoring activity

- *In progress*

The service is hosted by the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ partners. ILC will implement an OpenAPI-compliant proxy, which will be exposed in the H2IOSC marketplace to interface with the service provided by LINDAT.

Authentication

The integration of the CLARIN Service Provider Federation into Nanotec's authentication system is currently under evaluation.

Endpoints

- Main: <http://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/udpipe/api> (CLARIN-ERIC endpoint)
- Models: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/udpipe/api/models> (CLARIN-ERIC endpoint)
- Process: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/udpipe/api/process> (CLARIN-ERIC endpoint)

OAD

The following URL does not point to a standard OAD, but is rather a technical documentation <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/udpipe/api-reference.php>

ILC PI - Named Entity Recognition (based on NameTag)

Named Entity Recognition (based on NameTag): NameTag is an open-source tool for named entity recognition (NER). NameTag identifies and classifying entities in text. The

Classification categories are predefined, such as names of persons, locations, organizations, etc. The tool supports multilingual processing, uses advanced machine learning models, and allows custom training for specific domains. NameTag integrates seamlessly with Universal Dependencies and is widely used in text analysis, data enrichment, and search optimization.

This service is categorized as Linguistic Analysis; named entity recognition.

Current status

Refactoring activity is under evaluation as it will be deployed by using LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ guidelines.

Refactoring activity

- *In progress*

The service is hosted by the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ partners. ILC will implement an OpenAPI-compliant proxy, which will be exposed in the H2IOSC marketplace to interface with the service provided by LINDAT.

Authentication

The integration of the CLARIN Service Provider Federation into Nanotec's authentication system is currently under evaluation.

Endpoints

- Main: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/api> (CLARIN-ERIC endpoint)
- Models: <http://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/api/models> (CLARIN-ERIC endpoint)
- Process: <http://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/api/recognize> (CLARIN-ERIC endpoint)

OAD

The following URL does not point to a standard OAD, but is rather a technical documentation <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/api-reference.php>

ILC PI - Federated Content Search

Federated Content Search: The Federated Content Search (FCS) of CLARIN enables unified searching across distributed language resources and tools via a single interface retrieving real-time results without centralizing data. It connects diverse repositories using standardized protocols (SRU/CQL), allowing researchers to efficiently access, query, and analyze multilingual and multimodal language data. This system fosters resource discovery and interdisciplinary research in linguistics and the humanities.

It connects to diverse content sources, aggregates results, and presents them in a unified format. It simplifies content discovery, reduces data duplication, and enhances collaboration.

This service is categorized as Query and data extraction; Linguistic resources exploration and retrieval.

Current status

Refactoring activity is under evaluation as it will be deployed by using CLARIN-ERIC guidelines.

Refactoring activity

- *In progress*

ILC is analyzing the implementation of an OpenAPI-compliant services to the FCS services: <https://contentsearch.clarin.eu/>

Authentication

The integration of the CLARIN Service Provider Federation into Nanotec's authentication system is currently under evaluation.

Endpoints:

- ILC endpoint: <http://ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/fcs-korp-ep/sru>
- Aggregator: <https://contentsearch.clarin.eu/> (CLARIN-ERIC endpoint)

OAD:

The following URL does not point to a standard OAD, but is rather a technical documentation <https://clarin-eric.github.io/fcs-misc/fcs-core-2.0-specs/fcs-core-2.0.html>

ILC PI - TEI Publisher + eXist-db

TEI Publisher: TEI Publisher is an open-source framework for creating and publishing digital editions of texts encoded in the XML/TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) format. It enables users to display, search, and interact with TEI-encoded documents through customizable, user-friendly interfaces, making it an essential tool for digital humanities projects and scholarly text presentations.

eXist-db: eXist-db is an open-source, XML-based database and application platform designed for storing, querying, and managing XML data. It provides robust support for standards like XQuery and XSLT, making it ideal for applications in digital humanities, publishing, and content management systems. With its flexibility and extensibility, eXist-db enables rapid development of web applications that leverage structured XML data.

These services are categorized as Data representation and visualization; Linguistic resources visualization and presentation.

Current status

Refactoring activity under evaluation. The TEIPublisher API will be deployed in the context of H2IOSC services.

Refactoring activity

Refactoring activity under evaluation.

Authentication

The integration of the CLARIN Service Provider Federation into Nanotec's authentication system is currently under evaluation.

Endpoints

<https://teipublisher.com/exist/apps/tei-publisher/api.html> (no H2IOSC neither CLARIN endpoint)

OAD:

<https://teipublisher.com/exist/apps/tei-publisher/modules/lib/api.json> (no H2IOSC neither CLARIN endpoint)

ILC PI - Text Aligner

The Text Aligner service handles bidirectional string alignment using a variety of algorithms and approaches, leveraging embeddings and combining traditional methods like the Needleman-Wunsch Algorithm with advanced neural network techniques such as BERT Score. It relies on the string2string library (developed by the Stanford NLP lab) and BERTalign as key components. The string2string library is an open-source tool offering efficient algorithms for tasks such as alignment, distance measurement, search, and similarity analysis. It integrates traditional algorithms (e.g., Smith-Waterman, Wagner-Fisher, Knuth-Morris-Pratt) with advanced methods like BARTScore and BERTScore, provides visualization tools, and incorporates metrics like sacreBLEU and ROUGE, making it a versatile resource for natural language processing, bioinformatics, and computational social sciences.

This service is categorized as Data processing; Query and data extraction.

Current status

- Software Analysis and API design.

Refactoring activity

- In progress

Based on the string2string or BERTaligner software package, a functional analysis is underway to define the appropriate design for RESTful APIs.

Authentication

Not significant.

Endpoints:

- N/A

String2String (<https://github.com/stanfordnlp/string2string>) BertAlign (<https://github.com/bfsujason/bertalign>)

OAD

In development.

ILC PI - EpiLexO Editor - An interface for editing/creating linked language resources for ancient languages

EpiLexO: an interface for creating lexica for epigraphic languages conformant to Semantic Web principles linked to their testimonies (encoded in TEI-EpiDoc) and related bibliographies.

This service is categorized as Lexicon creation & management; Lexicon lookup & searching. The EpiLexO Editor is the editing GUI interface of the DigitAnt platform; built in Angular 11, it operates upon a set of independent software back-end components, mainly the LexO-server and the CASH-server. The application is designed to facilitate collaboration among scholars, enabling multiple researchers to work simultaneously on the same datasets in cooperation. The EpiLexO GUI is organised in 3 main sections (or columns), each of them providing a set of different functionalities for different data and information types. The column on the left contains the navigation trees for the main resources: corpus, lexicon, and (lexical) concepts; the column on the right side of the interface displays several panels that contain contextual and additional information such as links to related resources, bibliography, attestations, and metadata. The central column is the main working area devoted to lexicon editing and linking operations, in its 2 horizontal panels, one for Inscriptions, the other for lexical entries. The interface can be considered a functional working prototype, with core functionalities for lexicon processing, creation, and lookup implemented; it is currently in active use by the ItAnt project members. The interface supports basic editing and creation of linked language resources for ancient languages.

Current status

The service is ready to be deployed (upon request).

Refactoring activity

- *completed*

Software analysis

Authentication

Federated authentication is not yet implemented but will be integrated according to the general project standards.

Endpoints

https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/epilexo_demo/lexicon (CLARIN-IT endpoint)

OAD:

Not available

ILC PI - eScriptorium: a web platform for Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR)

eScriptorium is a web platform which integrates Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) through kraken HTR engine and cooperative proofreading of automated transcriptions. Through the HTR United Project not only new performant HTR models are provided, but the entire process of image acquisition / recognition / HTR model refinement / proofreading / deposit of digital resources is open and replicable, in compliance to the principle of Open Science.

Current status

The service is not yet active.

Refactoring activity

- N/A

Authentication

Federated authentication is not yet implemented but will be integrated according to the general project standards.

Endpoints

<https://escriptorium.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr> (CLARIN-IT endpoint, not yet installed)

OAD:

Not available

DARIAH

The DARIAH services listed here will be displayed via the marketplace and, where appropriate, will also be published on the DARIAH service platform, AEON. The core element underpinning the platform is an API manager, which is currently being implemented, based on WSO2 technology. Within the API manager, the federation authentication service based on an AAI developed by Nanotec will be integrated, while the authorisation part and related user role management will be developed at the infrastructure level.

It will be noted that, compared to the previous deliverable (D6.1), the services

- OVI CNR FI - Raw Data Ingestion Tool Suite
- OVI CNR FI - Semantic Data Ingestion Tool Suite
- OVI CNR FI - Data Management Tool Suite (RAISE-BE)
- OVI CNR FI - Data Visualization Tool Suite (RAISE-FE)
- OVI CNR FI - RAISE Atlante Module
- OVI CNR FI - RAISE Chronos Module

have been integrated into a single service called RAISE (formerly, for abuse of notation, RESTORE).

Finally, a certain affinity between the functionality of GATTO, TIGRO and TLIO may be noted; indeed, it cannot be ruled out that, in a possible future development, some of these functionalities may be merged, but for the time being this has not yet happened, and what follows is a presentation of the current situation.

Closing the list of DARIAH services are two services, the MetaFAIR Ecosystem and the Digital Philology Hub, which originate within the H2IOSC project, the former as a "fairificator" and resource manager, the latter as one of DARIAH's pilots. More description of both is given in the corresponding sections.

OVI CNR FI - TLIO, Tesoro della Lingua Italiana delle Origini

This tool falls into the "browsing and querying" category of dictionary studies. It is a web-based search application created by the Institute Opera del Vocabolario Italiano of the CNR. The system is designed to access the TLIO (Treasure of the Italian Language of Origins). It provides an interactive and user-friendly digital interface that allows users to navigate online through the historical lexicon of ancient Italian.

Current status

It still has to be servified, and it will be done later because it has a low priority service, as it does not belong to DARIAH's pilots. Nonetheless, there are no concerns about any hard issue emerging during the servification activity.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*
Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

Still not available (encompassed by `http://tlio.ovi.cnr.it/TLIO/ricTLIO2.php``)

OAD:

Still not available

OVI CNR FI - Pluto, Piattaforma Lessicografica Unica del Tesoro delle Origini

This tool is classified as a "browsing and querying" service in the realm of dictionary research. It's a web-based application being crafted by the CNR Opera del Vocabolario Italiano Institute to enable users to tap into the BTV (Bibliografia dei Testi Volgari), which stands as the most comprehensive compilation of bibliographic information on early Italian writings. The project, known as Pluto, seeks to progressively incorporate all TLIO-related resources and instruments into a unified framework, consolidating previously disparate databases and applications into a single, cohesive digital environment.

Current status

This component is yet to be serviced. The conversion will be scheduled for a later date due to its low-priority status, as it's not part of DARIAH's main pilot projects. However, there's confidence that the process of turning it into a service won't encounter any significant obstacles or complications.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*

Software analysis

- *In progress*

Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

Currently, `http://pluto.ovi.cnr.it/btv/testi_results/``,
`http://pluto.ovi.cnr.it/btv/autori_results/``.

OAD:

https://baltig.cnr.it/francesco.pinna/oas_wp6/-/tree/main/PLUTO

OVI CNR FI - GATTO, Gestione degli Archivi Testuali del Tesoro delle Origini

GATTO is a lexicographic software designed and developed at OVI, created for the construction, management and querying of the corpus of texts on which the Vocabolario Storico della Lingua Italiana, maintained and managed by OVI, is based. In its servification, GATTO will naturally include the features of GATTOweb (see D6.1), allowing the consultation of the corpus, both lemmatized and not, through a web interface.

Current status

It has yet to undergo the servification process, which will be addressed during the next stage due to its high priority, as it is part of DARIAH's pilot projects. However, there are no significant concerns regarding potential issues arising during the servification process.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*
Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

Still not available

OAD:

Still not available

OVI CNR FI - TIGRO, Tesoro Italiano delle Origini, gestore ricerche

Tigro is a lexicographic software designed and developed at OVI, originated as a spin-off and servification of the existing tool GATTO. It allows the construction and querying of corpora of texts, with an initial focus on lexicographic research and texts in ancient Italian, but with a built-in possibility of handling broader linguistic and research contexts. It is in active development. It consists of a web-based GUI along with a set of APIs that allow direct machine-to-machine interaction with both existing and newly defined corpora.

Current status

Beta version, only available on the OVI intranet.

Refactoring activity

- *In progress*
Integration with the authentication service developed by Nanotec, testing to get from beta to full 1.0 version

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

No public endpoint is currently publicly available; a test endpoint exists on the OVI intranet. A public endpoint will be made available as soon as the integration with the Auth service is completed.

OAD:

An OAS document has already been defined and it has been published at: [OAS on Baltig⁵](#)
However, it is still not complete as it misses some of the TIGRO's API.

OVI CNR FI - Mirabile, Archivio digitale della cultura medievale (owned by FEF and SISMELE)

MIRABILE is a knowledge management system dedicated to the study and research of medieval culture, encompassing the digital resources provided by SISMELE and FEF. The platform offers online tools that allow users to search through:

- Databases from various research projects in medieval studies, promoted by both institutions and their partners over several decades.
- Electronic versions of journals and collected works published by SISMELE. Edizioni del Galluzzo.

In this context, MIRABILE may serve as a data source, accessible by the services and platforms developed within H2IOSC, specifically by the first DARIAH's pilot, the Digital Philology Hub. Moreover, it may play an important role in the creation of domain-specific vocabularies and thesauri.

Current status

The servification process has not yet been carried out but is scheduled for the next phase, given its medium priority, as it is considered a "nice to have" component of DARIAH's pilot projects. Nonetheless, there are no major concerns about potential issues emerging during the servification.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*

⁵ CNR authentication required

Software analysis

- *In progress*
Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

Still not available

OAD:

Still not available

OVI CNR FI - EVT, Edition Visualization Technology

As part of the RESTORE project, DARIAH-IT, based at OVI, developed a customized version of the EVT (Edition Visualization Technology) application, which is intended to be further developed and employed for the creation of the H2IOSC Scientific Pilots. The original EVT is an open-source, lightweight tool designed to facilitate the creation of digital editions from TEI XML-encoded texts, removing the need for scholars to engage in web programming. It provides end users with a user-friendly interface to browse, explore, and study digital editions. DARIAH-IT's version of EVT was designed to offer advanced navigation features, allowing users to thoroughly explore the lexicographic details of a text. The DARIAH-IT team, as part of the RESTORE project, added support for the management and display of lexicographic data. OVI resources were used as a case study and can now be viewed in EVT with all their lexicographic components (such as lemmas, hyperlinks, and additional information). This enables the examination of different instances of a lemma within the same text, its normalized form, grammatical category, and more. Additionally, the newly introduced mode allows users to view both text and images, making it easier to consult digital facsimiles alongside text transcriptions within the same interface.

Current status

The service is currently on hold as we are assessing whether it is truly necessary for DARIAH's pilot projects. The external provider responsible for developing the Digital Philology Hub has already implemented an effective visualization tool using TEI publisher technology, which fully covers all the required features of EVT.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*

As its status remains on hold, we will not proceed with any further implementation

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used, unless we will keep the service status on hold.

Endpoints

Not available

OAD:

Not available

OVI CNR FI - RAISE - Restore dAta Integration Suite

RAISE, a spin-off of the RESTORE project, is a collection of tools for data ingestion, semantization, storage and visualization. Its main components are:

- A set of command-line tools to assist data managers in the tasks such as data ingestion, filtering, cleaning, semantization.
- A triple store (an instance of Openlink Virtuoso) enriched with custom APIs for data storage and querying
- A modular, customizable web-based GUI for data visualization.

Current status

The servification of the toolset is partial; some of the services are offline-only (source code is available, users are responsible for their use and implementation, with limited support available from the Dariah team).

Refactoring activity

- *In progress*
Servification of additional services, development of the web interfaces to improve interoperability and reusability, adding support for different DB solutions, Integration with the authentication service developed by Nanotec.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

No public endpoint is currently available. Test endpoints exist on the OVI intranet for those services that already have APIs. Public endpoints for API-enabled services will be made available as soon as the integration with the Nanotec Auth service is completed.

OAD:

OAS documents are already defined for those services that are API-enabled, but they are not publicly available; they will be made available as soon as the APIs are opened to the internet.

OVI CNR FI - TRAME, Text and manuscript transmission of the Middle Ages in Europe (owned by FEF)

The TRAME initiative, backed by the Italian Ministry of Education and led by the Ezio Franceschini Foundation, seeks to enhance the evolution and interoperability of web-based resources focusing on medieval manuscript heritage. At its core, TRAME aims to foster synergy among digital archives housing scanned images of Middle Age texts, alongside their physical characteristics, literary significance, and cultural impact within the broader context of Europe's historical narrative. This collaborative effort brings together various repositories to create a more comprehensive and accessible resource for scholars and enthusiasts of medieval literature and history.

Current status

The transformation of this element into a functional service is still pending. Given that it's not included in DARIAH's primary experimental initiatives, this task has been assigned a lower priority and will be addressed at a future point. Despite the delay, there's no anticipation of any major challenges or roadblocks arising during the service conversion process.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*
Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

`<http://trame.fefonlus.it/trame/index.php>`

OAD:

Still not available.

OVI-FI - MFE: MetaFAIR Ecosystem

MFE is a Platform for the integrated management of digitised manuscripts.

Designed for researchers, scholars and institutions such as libraries, archives and museums, it enables them to catalogue, preserve and enhance documents in a unified environment.

Some of its key features include:

- Cataloguing: Supports national and international cataloguing standards, enabling an accurate description of cultural assets.
- Digitisation: Manages digitisation processes, ensuring the acquisition and archiving of images and documents in digital format.
- Digital Preservation: Ensures the long-term preservation of digital content, implementing strategies for the preservation of data integrity and accessibility.
- Access and use: Provides tools for consultation and research of digital collections, facilitating public or restricted access to materials.
- Integration: Integrates with other information systems and platforms, facilitating interoperability and data exchange between different cultural institutions.

Current status

MFE is in the development phase. Its first release, with basic functionalities, will be in January 2025.

Refactoring activity

As a bare new DARIAH service built within H2IOSC, it has been developed in compliance with the project's policies and best practices, so refactoring is not planned.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager is used.

Endpoints

` <https://dev-ovi-metafad.devworkbench.it/> `

OAD:

Still not available.

E-RIHS

E-RIHS (European research infrastructure for Heritage Science) offers access to cutting-edge laboratories, tools, and data and provides training opportunities in Heritage Science. Refactored E-RIHS services in WP6 offer improved access to valuable products targeting different scientific communities and areas, ranging from digital fabrication, interactive presentation of 3D/nD datasets on the web, geometry processing services, capture services (analytics), sensor networks for monitoring, AI/ML processing services and remote access to acquisition systems for heritage science.

ISTI PI - Digital Fabrication Laboratory Virtual Access

We plan to establish a software infrastructure for allowing virtual access to ISTI-PI Digital Fabrication Laboratory within the framework of the H2IOSC project's WP6. The primary objective is to facilitate researchers in obtaining physical replicas from their digital models. This will be achieved by expanding the existing server-based mesh processing infrastructure, originally designed for creating multiresolution representations of 3D models, to incorporate fabrication-oriented processing operations.

- The Digital Fabrication Laboratory at ISTI-PI will house a range of high-end and consumer-grade digital fabrication equipment. As part of its service offering within the E-RIHS network, ISTI-PI will implement a platform for users to upload 3D models for printing.
- The platform will process the uploaded models, preparing them for fabrication tasks. Users will have access to tools for identifying and rectifying potential problems in their models, thereby streamlining the fabrication workflow and enhancing its predictability.
- This platform will leverage ISTI-CNR's existing open-source mesh processing framework, MeshLab, and its server-side Python counterpart for on-demand processing.
- The existing software infrastructure for processing user-uploaded meshes, initially intended for creating streamable multiresolution representations of complex 3D assets, will be augmented to include fabrication-specific mesh processing functionalities

Deployment:

We are refactoring existing base code to allow simpler deployment on cluster-based server architecture like the one provided by H2IOSC, using containerization framework like docker. We are planning to generate an OAS descriptor for the refactored service to enhance its discoverability within the H2IOSC framework. We are evaluating various possibilities about the actual hosting of the platform.

ISPC CT – hyMOLAB

The hyMOLAB service is focused on innovative acquisition systems for heritage science for strengthening the Italian Nodes of E-RIHS. ISPC CT is contributing with the design and development of a system that integrates a robotic arm and a complex analytical system (henceforth 'Cobot') for the investigation of 2D or 3D surfaces. Mechanic components of the Cobot are active and integrated with its control software. The implementation of dynamic Z correction is currently ongoing, as well as the the development of the remotization platform (hardware) and the digital platform to be used in the remote measurements. A specific focus of this stage is to verify that individual hardware components are functioning and are correctly integrated. The measuring head for simultaneous MA-XRF and VIS-NIR RIS has been designed and installed on the robotic arm. The system has been integrated with an x-axis to increase the degree of movement and with the Cobot software to control it. In progress is also the design and development of the subsystem for the scanning and virtual replication of the artwork and the surrounding environment, to be integrated with a 'safety system' to ensure safe measuring conditions for the artwork and compliance with radioprotection guidelines.

To promote accessibility and FAIR principles, a user-friendly GUI is being developed, where users will see the real-time processing of spectral data-cubes and actively interact with the provider to extract chemical information on the analysed object. Further data processing will be also accessible to the user, with image/spectrum analysis. Users will be able to download the resulting image/data files and reports (.tiff, .xlsx, .pdf). This interaction is intended to support specific users' needs and to be eventually re-shaped depending on the research questions. The acquisition of spectral data from large surfaces, either when the hyMOLAB provider is physically present or controls the system remotely

Deployment

The tool is currently not implemented as a service. The hardware/software systems to collect, analyse, process and visualise data from artworks will be further implemented on-premises exploiting FAIR design approaches once all the hardware components are correctly assembled and tested. The service shall be deployed at ISPC CT depending on the specific object/location of the investigation, then moved to the user location within the frame of the E-RIHS network. The envisioned user scenario implies transportation and installation of the system in situ, when the Cobot will be active and integrated with its software counterpart.

ISPC CT - AI/ML solution for multimodal datasets

Network trained and tested for usage with X-ray fluorescence (XRF) instrumentation of ISPC CT. It has been successfully used for the analysis of a number of cultural heritage objects. At this point this includes paintings both modern and historic, Egyptian amulets and Herculaneum papyri. The outlook is to further develop the analysis to other analytical techniques followed by extensions to multimodal datasets. We have built an AI

solution for combined analysis of XRF and X-ray diffraction (XRD) which is now being tested. In the future we plan to construct a solution for combined analysis of XRF and RIS imaging.

The network architecture and trained networks are planned to be publicly available in the future.

AI/ML approaches provide many advantages during data analysis and processing. It allows users to analyse XRF data on-the-fly during measurement providing a high-fidelity output in the real time while significantly reducing expertise needed. This is particularly useful in on-the-site measurements as it provides guidance helping to improve quality and relevance of the results. Further, such analysis is also closely connected to the remotization task introduced in WP 6.7.

Another scenario is advanced analysis of large multimodal datasets remotely. With growing size and complexity of data obtained by the modern hyperspectral instruments the increased the demand on computational power, time and expertise required for the analysis.

Servification of the AI solutions is designed to help users to perform analysis remotely without access to the computational resources. At the current state the tool takes as an input XRF datacube and generates elemental composition maps. The foreseen inputs are multimodal datacubes.

Deployment:

The tool is currently not implemented as a service, but the creation of the service is underway, where a functional prototype has been developed. The service will be deployed at ISPC CT datacenter.

ISPC CT - Multimodal datasets visualization tool

Toolsuite for real-time interactive analysis of XRF datasets. It implements both classical deconvolution approaches as well AI/ML for the data analysis described above. While the software is still under development it is already being used during measurements that are part of the MOLAB platform of E-RIHS. Tool for analysis of XRD datasets. The tool aims to provide capability for automatic and semiautomatic phase identification using XRD and hyperspectral data. The analysis of the XRD dataset is done using classical Algorithms. Recently we have developed a prototype AI for the combined analysis of XRD and XRF data. The development of tools for analysis of other hyperspectral analytical techniques are planned in the future. Currently we are extending our model to combine analysis XRF and RIS data.

At the moment there is a lack of software for advanced interactive interrogation of multimodal datasets. This tool aims to allow the user to interact with data obtained using different analytical techniques provided within the MOLAB platform of E-RIHS at once in a concise manner.

The inputs are experimental datasets. The general outputs are graphs and images. In practice this encompasses various scientific results of interest such as elemental composition maps and/or maps indicating materials present.

Deployment:

The tool is currently not implemented as a service but is used as an on-premises software. The service implementation is currently underway. It will be deployed at ISPC CT datacenter.

ISPC RM – Kpto

The E-RIHS Kpto service offers a set of functionalities to track and record interactive sessions performed in remote infrastructural nodes, public exhibits or online web-applications – targeting analytics.

Service requirements led to the design of scalable architecture able to handle and track incoming anonymized interaction states via network connection – and storing them on a dedicated capture hub, or multiple capture hubs (Fanini & Gosti 2024). The Kpto service can be used standalone, or as a part of a wider pipeline involving a suite of web-based services dedicated to analytics workflows, allowing examination/filtering of incoming raw data, and then process such data using for instance Machine Learning models (e.g. pilot 7.7 “Interlumo”).

The service was developed ex-novo within the H2IOSC project, following guidelines from D6.1 and designing a flexible set of routines to be exposed and accessed by scientific communities willing to track generic interactive sessions.

A flexible architecture was designed in terms of session tracking and retrieval, custom state definition (e.g., custom attributes to track), reliability considerations and an on-demand model. The final protocol between the client application and the capture hub where the service is deployed, is here described:

1. The client application requests a new session, including the intended attributes to track (e.g. 2D/3D coordinates, time, etc.)
2. If the capture service responds successfully, a new session is initiated on the hub and the unique ID is sent to the client
3. The client application is now able to send progressive data chunks to the hub, with custom policies

For the first step, the client application formalizes a list of attributes that will be tracked during the session. This may include spatial attributes (like virtual/physical 3D locations, eye movements, focal points, HMD location in physical space, GPS coordinates, etc.), interaction states related to the application logic or equipment (like BCI headsets’ EEG voltages for each channel, wearable device signals, sensors data, etc.) or other attributes.

Session ID allows access to current record (CSV or other formats) via REST API, to retrieve tracked data.

OAD:

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/phoenixbf/kpto/refs/heads/main/services/openapi.json>

Git repository:

<https://github.com/phoenixbf/kpto>

Deployment:

The service will be deployed on a dedicated and public hub inside the “Area della Ricerca di Roma 1” (CNR) using a cluster model, and it will be part of the H2IOSC pilot 7.7 “Interlumo”. A docker image is also provided

Authentication:

The service is based on Node.js and an integration with federated authentication service (SSO) developed by CNR Nanotec is foreseen.

ISPC NA/RM – ATON (WebXR Services for HS)

ATON⁶ is an open-source framework (Fanini et al. 2021) developed by CNR ISPC based on large open-source ecosystems (such as THREE.js and Node.js) and modern web standards to create interactive, liquid and collaborative Web3D/WebXR apps targeting Heritage Science. Its adaptive presentation layer allows interactive 3D visualization on all devices, ranging from mobile (smartphones, tablets) up to PC/workstations and immersive XR devices, without any installation required for final users. It offers a modular architecture and event-driven API to craft rich, immersive or collaborative Web3D tools or experiences. It is based on interoperable web standards allowing maximum reuse and integration with other services, especially within the H2IOSC complex ecosystem.

Within H2IOSC, the service will be used by different E-RIHS WP7 pilots, specifically: “SENENSE: Spatial hEritage scieNce oNline Sensor Environment” (ISPC LE), “Illuminated Manuscripts” (ISPC LE), “HeriVerse” (ISPC LE), “Interlumo” (ISPC RM) and “Prototyping platform for Virtual / Physical Exhibitions” (ISPC FI).

Refactoring:

Under task 6.3, refactoring activities focused on:

- A complete re-design of existing REST API
- Re-design of the plug&play web-apps architecture
- Implementation of plugins (“flares”) architecture
- Re-design of core micro-services for improved flexibility (e.g. custom authentication models, etc...)
- Re-design of the User Interface and its components
- Improved injection and extraction of copyright information from 3D models
- Improved collaborative components

Guidelines and best practices established in WP6 and its interactions with other WPs, allowed to redesign the new REST API (v2) around specific resources:

- Collection items (3D models – pointclouds or meshes, panoramic content, media, etc.)
- 3D scenes (arrangements of collection items)
- Users
- Apps

⁶ <https://aton.ispc.cnr.it/site/>

- Flares (plugins)

For each of the above, a persistent identifier is provided for retrieval or manipulation via REST API. Refactoring actions were also carried out to facilitate the integration of the service with ongoing development of a few E-RIHS pilots requiring it. Previous REST API (v1) will be still operational for a time to guarantee backwards compatibility.

H2IOSC project and the variety of the E-RIHS pilots requiring this service, indeed led to focus several activities on further improving extensibility. The plug&play architecture of the service was redesigned to accelerate integration of *vertical* web-applications (e.g. E-RIHS pilots with specific focus or domain), allowing single instances to host one or more Web3D/WebXR applications. This allows also flexibility in terms of physical deployment (e.g. single instance with several apps, or more instances handling separate apps) depending on datacenters availability and request volumes foreseen.

“Flares” (plugins) were designed and implemented under task 6.3 for *horizontal* extension: similarly to apps architecture, flares can be plugged dynamically on a given instance, to enrich both client and server functionalities. A single web-app (e.g. a pilot) can thus require one or more plugins, depending on project requirements. To assess such functionalities, a flare is being developed targeting survey domain (survey-flare). The flare system will be also used to provide integration with the federated authentication service (SSO) developed by CNR Nanotec, or other authentication models.

Figure 2: vertical (apps) and horizontal (flares) extensibility of the refactored service

OAD:

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/phoenixbf/aton/master/services/API/openapi.json>

Git repository:

<https://github.com/phoenixbf/aton>

Deployment:

The service will be deployed in Naples and Lecce Datacenters, using cluster mode. Depending on specific pilots' requirements, minor instances could be deployed in other nodes of the H2IOSC federation. A docker image is also provided.

Authentication:

The service is based on Node.js and an integration with federated authentication service (SSO) developed by CNR Nanotec is foreseen. This will also allow a few E-RIHS pilots using this service to directly exploit SSO for custom logic.

IMATI GE - GRAVIFIX tool

The GRAVIFIX tool can be applied to single closed objects represented as triangle meshes, which needs simplification and/or cleaning (solving geometric or topological errors). The input model must be a triangle mesh, possibly having holes, in .ply format. Small holes will be patched, while bigger holes will be maintained. If more connected components are present, GraviFix will discard the smaller components and work on the biggest component only. GraviFix will start analysing the input file, providing statistics (e.g., number of vertices) and a report on the quality of the input mesh. If there are geometrical or topological flaws, GraviFix will proceed with the cleaning operations. Then, GraviFix proceeds to simplify the model adaptively, i.e., maintaining the small surface features as much as possible. Besides the output models, GraviFix also produces a text file, reporting details about the performed operations and a cumulative ascii file with statistics about all the processed files.

Current status

The service is not yet available.

Refactoring activity

The service has not been refactored yet. However, the set of *functions/routines to be exposed* by the service have been identified, and the HTTP verbs to be used for this service are: GET, POST.

Authentication

Federated authentication is not yet implemented but will be integrated according to the general project standards and E-RIHS policies.

Endpoints

Not available yet.

OAD:

Not available yet

IMATI GE - 3D ANNOTATION tool

The 3D annotation tool allows associating textual tags to parts of 3D models, represented as triangular meshes. The textual tags derive from a controlled vocabulary and are used to annotate areas, lines and points of a 3D mesh, which have an interest for the user (e.g. a curator, an archaeologist in the current implementation). The 3D annotation tool is included in an IMATI software platform for the analysis and restoration of cultural heritage artifacts. The platform is client-server and includes a desktop interface able to support actively users with a rich visual context for the exploration of digital fragments. In particular, the desktop client focuses on graphics interaction with the 3D digital assets, and provides functionalities to visualise geometric properties, perform measurements on artifacts, annotate their parts and execute algorithms such as the feature recognition and virtual reassembly of artifacts.

Current status

The service is not yet available.

Refactoring activity

The service has not been refactored yet. However, the set of *functions/routines to be exposed* by the service have been identified, and the HTTP verbs to be used for this service are: GET, POST, PUT, PATCH, DELETE.

Authentication

Federated authentication is not yet implemented but will be integrated according to the general project standards and E-RIHS policies.

Endpoints

Not available yet.

OAD:

Not available yet

IMATI GE - SimilarityLib

This Toolkit contains a number of functions for evaluating geometric characteristics, building descriptors and computing similarity distances and their combination. It contains the routines to elaborate a number of geometric properties: area, volume, mean curvature, shape index, shape diameter function, minimal bounding box, thickness, RGB to Cielab coordinates conversion; descriptors: compactness, Non normalized shape distributions, histograms, persistence diagrams; similarity distances: L1, LP, Earth Mover's distance, Bhattacharya distance, matching distance; and the combination of several distances.

Current status

The service is not yet available.

Refactoring activity

The service has not been refactored yet. However, the set of *functions/routines to be exposed* by the service have been identified, and the HTTP verbs to be used for this service are: GET, POST.

Authentication

Federated authentication is not yet implemented but will be integrated according to the general project standards and E-RIHS policies.

Endpoints

Not available yet.

OAD:

Not available yet

ISPC LE - SENNSE: Wireless sensor networks for cultural heritage conservation and monitoring

The Wireless sensor network will gather and transmit measured data on cultural heritage, making them available for remote analysis, post-processing and visualization at the DIGILAB level. From the hardware point of view, microcontroller unit-based modules will be in direct contact with the distributed sensors and actuators at different sites on one side and datacenters on the other side through wired and wireless communication protocols and standards.

The Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol, offering lightweight and efficient communication mechanisms, has been selected for connecting WSN nodes and facilitating data exchange.

The data acquired by the WSN management middleware platform are sent to an open-source software DIGILAB component that allows the analysis, post-processing and presentation of heterogeneous geolocated data in the domain of cultural heritage. The component will request the data from the WSN using its API and present them through interactive and customizable multi-tenant dashboards.

The designed large-scale WSNs can enable remote monitoring and smart control of cultural heritage sites, reducing the need for physical interventions and enhancing the overall efficiency of preservation efforts. Moreover, the platform will allow the creation of connections between the collected data in several research contexts of the cultural heritage field, promoting their sharing and accessibility.

Due to the heterogeneity of monitored sites and technologies used, the design of a WSN will be based on abstract models of its components. In particular, the creation of the networks will consist of a first step in which it will be possible to create the WSN as a composition of abstract elements, and a second step in which the abstract elements will be instantiated through their configuration.

A first phase of study involved the research for devices and sensors available on the market that can be applied in the field of cultural heritage monitoring. These devices and sensors detect environmental and structural parameters, capable of providing information on the state of tangible assets and their evolution in time. Characteristics taken into consideration were low energy consumption, low cost, and the communication way.

Subsequently, use cases that best represented the large case of situations in which these devices could be applied were studied.

Based on this information, the requirements of the software platform called SENNSE (Spatial hERitage science oNline Sensor Environment) were defined.

In particular, the following modules will be implemented:

- SENNSE WSN Modeler: allows to model the WSN by means of a visual interface. The WSN will be represented in the form of a graph, i.e. a set of nodes (abstract node) connected each other. Each node and its link have specific properties, e.g. gateway, sensor, etc. Users can model their own WSN starting from a model (WSN template) or from scratch as a composition of abstract nodes. The choice of the WSN template is guided by the characteristics of the site/object to be monitored and the purposes of the monitoring itself. The output of the SENNSE WSN Modeler editor is the abstract WSN model;
- The SENNSE WSN Configurator is a full-web application that allows the configuration of the abstract elements (abstract node) of the abstract WSN model defined in the SENNSE-WSN Modeler. The configuration of the abstract model allows to obtain the WSN concrete model;
- The SENNSE User Manager allows to define and manage the different types of local users and to interface with external “authentication and identification” systems;
- The Rule System: is the module that defines the rules through which specific actions are activated when a particular event occurs (based on the data received from the sensors), such as, for example, sending notifications via e-mail;

Current status

The service will be deployed in Lecce Datacenter. The hardware part is under development at SciFablab and DhiLab in Lecce, while as regard the software part, a mandate was given to an external software company.

Refactoring activity

As a bare new E-RIHS service built within H2IOSC, it has been developed in compliance with the project’s policies and best practices, so refactoring is not planned.

Authentication:

The service authentication will be integrated with federated authentication service (SSO) developed by CNR Nanotec is foreseen. Moreover, the user profile to access specific service features will be stored inside DIGILAB platform (see WP 3.1). DIGILAB platform will provide explicit API to allow the access to user profile

Endpoints:

not yet available

OAD:

Still not available

OPERAS

OPERAS does not have refactoring activities because it did not have services already developed. Research and cataloguing environments, such as Leibniz's Correspondents and Acquaintances, will be transferred to the new infrastructure.

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